

STRUCTURE AND EVOLUTION OF A DEBRIS CLOUD IN THE EARLY PHASES

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The early phases of a debris cloud from an instantaneous fragmentation on orbit are dominated by the effect of the two-body gravitational force on the delta- v imparted on each fragment, which gives an in-track spreading of the cloud. This spreading is seen to form radial bands opposite to the fragmentation point. The bands may be motivated by straightforward orbit mechanics. Accurate density maps are computed with the transformation of variables technique, which opens a world of *cloud dynamics* to contrast with the point dynamics of traditional astrodynamics. Structure and evolution of the bands and finer details are noted and discussed.

INTRODUCTION

When an instantaneous fragmentation happens on orbit, a single object suddenly becomes multiple objects, and the orbits of each of these pieces will be different from the original, *source* orbit. In fact, the fragmentation adds a random impulsive delta- v to each piece, and analysis may proceed as would a maneuver of such a type. Because this delta- v has in general no constraints, except perhaps a limit to its magnitude, the trajectory of such pieces can be almost anywhere physically possible.

For decades, researchers have employed various techniques to study the evolution of the “cloud” of fragments. Jehn [1] divided the post-fragmentation time interval into four phases, labeled “A,” “B,” “C,” and “D.” In phase A, the cloud of fragments is a pulsating ellipsoid, being still confined relatively close the source trajectory. The pulsation is seen to occur every orbital period; the extent of the cloud decreases and hence its density increases as it returns to the fragmentation point. In phase B, the shape of the cloud is a torus with a pinch point and pinch line. This may occur as soon as a few hours after fragmentation; what drives the spreading of fragments into the toroidal ring matching the source orbit is a velocity change component in the in-track direction that changes the orbital periods of the fragments. In phase C, perturbations, notably the J_2 geopotential perturbation, cause the nodal regression which smears out the torus into a spherical shell truncated at the polar caps. Finally in phase D, if the orbit is low enough, the evenly distributed band loses population to atmospheric drag lowering and ultimately deorbiting the fragments. In this study, we focus on phases A and B.

Hujzak [2], almost simultaneously with Jehn, derived a nonlinear dynamical model of the relative motion for the purpose of analysis of debris density from breakup through what Jehn would

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call phase B. By including select nonlinear terms and using a generalization of the Hill-Clohessy-Wiltshire equations for elliptical orbits, he was able to derive equations useful even far from the source orbit. He shows the inverse of the relative motion transformation is an approximate solution for the whole orbit Lambert (boundary value) problem. Including the geopotential J_2 perturbation, he is able to analyze debris density differentially as function of breakup velocity distribution. He found that particle density can vary by four orders of magnitude, and attributes increases in density away from the pinch point to perturbations. While we find the relative motion approach too limiting and therefore take a different approach, we regard Hujsak's study as a novel and pioneering idea for debris cloud evolution studies, and in a very significant sense inspired our present undertaking. His claim of four orders of magnitude is plausible, but concentrations of density occur even in an unperturbed model.

Often, these analyses proceed with explicit or implicit assumptions of the initial velocity distribution. Sometimes, for example, isotropic, or uniform in all directions, sometimes uniformly distributed in magnitude within some bound. The analysis may be based on some established fragmentation model, such as the NASA model [3], but more often it is not. There is much that can be concluded without a specific creation model, but having such a model allows one to investigate in greater depth the collective behavior of the fragments.

The purpose of this study is to determine the distribution in space of the fragments after a fixed period of time, and to provide the tools needed to make such studies in the future relatively easy. We have taken a fresh approach in this study. In order to find the distribution in space at the end of the time interval from the distribution in velocity at the beginning, we use the transformation of variables technique. This then provides a set of data which can be used to apply to any velocity distribution to determine the spatial distribution. The spatial distribution we seek is a function giving the *normalized number density* at any point in space, and it is measured in units of km^{-3} . Equally, this can be considered a probability density function; for example, the probability of the finding single vehicle in a location after a maneuver of uncertain Δv .

The transformation of variables method tells us how to compute a density after mapping the domain space through a transformation. It needs two pieces of information: the inverse image points under the initial velocity to final position mapping, and the determinant of the Jacobian of the map at each of those points. Once those have been computed for a point in the domain space of the transformation (velocities), the data may be saved as a distribution map, and the computation of a later spatial distribution from an initial velocity distribution may be performed as a value look-up, multiplication and addition, a relatively fast calculation.

In orbital terms, the initial velocity to final position mapping is, because the initial position is assumed fixed, simply the initial value problem for orbit dynamics. Here, unperturbed two-body (Kepler) motion is assumed, and the propagator used are the Lagrange coefficients f and g . The inverse map needed is the two-point boundary value problem, i.e., the Lambert problem. From every point r_2 at the end of the time interval and from the fixed initial location of the fragmentation r_1 , the task is to find the initial velocities \dot{r}_1 that solve the two-body motion. Then, for each of those initial values, to find the determinant of the Jacobian of the orbit propagation problem.

Astrodynamics, and before it, celestial mechanics, has been focused on *point dynamics*, that is, how a single satellite (or planet) moves about a single attracting body. For unperturbed motion particularly, this problem is well in hand; not just the initial value problem of orbit propagation, but the boundary value, or Lambert, problem is as well. What we propose here is new ground: that

Figure 1. Location of fragments after 24 hours from an orbit $a = 7278$ km projected to the source orbital plane; the red “x” marks the fragmentation point

point dynamics induces a *cloud dynamics*, an evolution of a density distribution over time. This is significantly more difficult to compute than the point dynamics case, but the rewards are potentially very large.

As a first step to understanding the evolution of fragments, we undertook a small study: a simulation involving a simple propagation of a few thousand fragments from a single point. This yielded a very noticeable pattern in the distribution which can be motivated with simple orbit mechanics. This is the topic of the next section. The search for an exact solution in the general case then spurred the cloud dynamics approach via transformation of variables, which is discussed in the following sections.

ANTIPODAL BANDS

Figure 1 shows the spatial distribution of fragments after twenty-four hours from a sun-synchronous low-earth (altitude 900 km, $a = 7278$ km) orbit projected into the source orbital plane. The velocities at the fragmentation point are distributed isotropically with Δv magnitude distributed according to the NASA breakup model EVOLVE [3], then propagated using a two-body propagator. (Drag and 6×6 geopotential effects, included here, makes little difference to the unperturbed result in this picture.) There is a very clear macroscopic structure to the fragments in configuration space after one day: the bands that are seen opposite (*antipodal* to) the fragmentation point. The number of bands increases with time initially and they move outward, eventually dying off.

To understand why these bands exist, simplify the initial change in velocity to be only tangential to the circular orbit of the source. In that case, we have the first part of a Hohmann transfer. Consider the arrival of each fragment at the antipodal line (in other words, 180 degrees from the fragmentation point). Since the delta- v was tangential to the circular orbit, the new perigee or apogee is on that line; it will be perigee if the direction of change was opposite the direction of motion, and apogee if it is in the same direction. As this is a perigee-to-apogee or apogee-to-perigee transfer, the time of flight is an odd multiple of one half the orbital period of the new orbit. In other words, the fragment makes $N + 1/2$ orbits between the fragmentation and the arrival at the antipodal point for some integer $N \geq 0$.

This means that when looking at the antipodal line at time t after the fragmentation, the semimajor axis has a discrete set of possible values,

$$a = \sqrt[3]{\mu \left[\frac{t}{(2N+1)\pi} \right]^2} \quad (1)$$

for integer $N \geq 0$. As a consequence, the antipodal geocentric distance is

$$\bar{r} = 2a - r = 2\sqrt[3]{\mu \left[\frac{t}{(2N+1)\pi} \right]^2} - r, \quad (2)$$

if the geocentric distance at fragmentation is r . It is easy to see the bands in this formula: the sequence $N = 0, 1, \dots$ produces successively smaller terms in the cube root, which means \bar{r} is smaller. So the outermost band is the half-orbit case, the next one closer to the earth is the one-and-a-half orbit case, and so on. There is a maximum N for a given time t because otherwise the semimajor axis becomes low enough that perigee will be inside the earth,

$$N < \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{t}{\pi} \sqrt{\mu \left(\frac{2}{R_\delta + r} \right)^3} - 1 \right]. \quad (3)$$

This limit will increase as time goes on. After sufficient time t , low values of N are limited by the maximum energy available in the fragmentation. To travel only one half orbit in a long time t requires that semimajor axis, and thus apogee radius, be very high. This requires a very large delta- v which may not be available in the fragmentation.

When there is a radial component to the delta- v , finding the location of the bands in geocentric distance on the antipodal axis is more complicated, but reduces to a simple formula that is independent of the radial velocity component v_r . Since the true anomaly of the fragmentation point (and antipodal point) on the new orbit can be any value, the antipodal distance must be computed generally. The sum of the antipodal and fragmentation geocentric distances is

$$r + \bar{r} = \frac{2p}{1 - e^2 \cos^2 \theta} = \frac{2a(1 - e^2)}{1 - e^2 \cos^2 \theta} \quad (4)$$

for fragmentation true anomaly θ , semimajor axis a , eccentricity e , and semilatus rectum p . The velocity components may be computed from the known velocity in the perifocal frame by rotation by the true anomaly,

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_r \\ v_\perp \end{bmatrix} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{p}} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -\sin \theta \\ e + \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{p}} \begin{bmatrix} e \sin \theta \\ 1 + e \cos \theta \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

The antipodal distance (at true anomaly $\theta + \pi$) is then seen to be a function of the tangential velocity only

$$\bar{r} = \frac{p}{1 - e \cos \theta} = \frac{\mu p}{2\mu - h v_{\perp}} = \frac{h^2}{2\mu - r v_{\perp}^2} = \frac{r^2 v_{\perp}^2}{2\mu - r v_{\perp}^2}, \quad (6)$$

or, in simplified form

$$\bar{r} = r \left(\frac{2\mu}{r v_{\perp}^2} - 1 \right)^{-1}. \quad (7)$$

This formula gives the geocentric distance when the object is on the antipodal line. When the orbit is circular, it gives $\bar{r} = r$, as it should, because $v_{\perp} = v = \sqrt{\mu/r}$.

From the speed and geocentric distance at the fragmentation point, the semimajor axis may be computed, so that after an elapsed time

$$t = (2N + 1)\pi \sqrt{\frac{a^3}{\mu}} \quad (8)$$

(from eq. (1)), that fragment will be on the antipodal line a distance \bar{r} from the geocenter. This explains where and when each piece will be on the antipodal line. It is clear that the existence of the bands persists even when there's a radial component of velocity, because for a given time, only a finite set of semimajor axes will be on the antipodal line, and their geocentric distance is determined solely by their tangential component of velocity.

We would like something more general than this, however. First, we'd like to know the structure anywhere, not just the antipodal line, and possibly arising from velocity in three Cartesian directions, not just two. In order to do that, we need to make a density map, in which we find the distribution of fragments in space at fixed time, instead of the customary "ephemeris" view of the distribution of a piece over time. In the language of fluid mechanics, this is a shift from a Lagrangian to the Eulerian view. Developing the map computation is the subject of the next section.

AN ORBITAL DENSITY MAP

An *orbital density map* as we define it is the density of orbiting objects in Cartesian space around the earth. This density is a function of the position, and of time. It may be a distribution of actual objects, such as fragments, but it may also be a probability distribution, which can be considered the distribution of virtual objects. A probability density or normalized number density function will integrate to one over the whole volume; a general density function will not have a specified integral, and might integrate to the total number of pieces, for example.

In order to find the density map, we will need to know the location of the fragmentation r_1 and the distribution of velocities. The distribution of locations $r_2(t)$ for an elapsed time t can be computed from orbit mechanics using the *transformation of variables* technique for density functions. This is a fairly time-consuming computation, but the most time-consuming part need be done only once for a given r_1 ; after that, different initial velocity distributions may be mapped with essentially only the computational burden of a look-up of values and a matrix multiplication.

The transformation (or change) of variables technique [4] can be stated simply. Given a function F from a space X to a space Y , a density function G_X in the space X can be transformed into one in the space Y by summing over all the points in the inverse image $F^{-1}(y)$ ($y \in Y$) divided by the

absolute value of the determinant of the Jacobian matrix of F

$$G_Y(y) = \sum_{x \in F^{-1}(y)} \frac{G_X(x)}{|\det J_F(x)|}, \quad (9)$$

where x and y can be vectors. The Jacobian matrix J_F is the matrix of partial derivatives of the function F . When the inverse image is a continuum rather than a discrete set of points, the sum must be replaced with an integral.

In the present application, the space X is three dimensional, the velocity at the fragmentation point, and the space Y , also three dimensional, is the location of the fragment at a fixed later time. We seek the orbital density function G_Y whose plot should resemble fig. 1 given the same initial velocity distribution.

For each value of the elapsed time after the fragmentation, the function G_Y must be computed for all points. However, once computed and stored, the values x in the inverse image of each point y , and the corresponding Jacobian determinant $|\det J_f(x)|$ may merely be looked up in a velocity distribution function G_X from which G_Y can be rapidly calculated.

There are clearly two pieces to the problem: finding the inverse images $F^{-1}(y)$ and computing the forward Jacobian determinant. In the orbital context, the forward function F is the initial value problem for orbit mechanics; given an initial position \mathbf{r}_1 and velocity $\dot{\mathbf{r}}_1$, find the position after time t , \mathbf{r}_2 and $\dot{\mathbf{r}}_2$. The inverse image calculation amounts to the two-point boundary value, or Lambert, problem. These are covered in order in the next two sections.

THE INITIAL VALUE PROBLEM

The perturbed point propagation, or initial value problem for orbit mechanics, is one that mathematicians, scientists, and engineers have struggled with for centuries, and active research on precision propagation continues to this day. In this paper, we only concern ourselves with unperturbed propagation, and there exists a method most suited for this application, the Lagrange f and g coefficients.

Because an orbit lies in a plane, any point on the orbit and any velocity vector can be described by two vectors that span the plane. Because they cannot be colinear, the initial position \mathbf{r}_1 and velocity $\dot{\mathbf{r}}_1$ may serve as those basis vectors, with suitable coefficients:

$$\mathbf{r}_2 = f(t)\mathbf{r}_1 + g(t)\dot{\mathbf{r}}_1 \quad (10a)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}}_2 = \dot{f}(t)\mathbf{r}_1 + \dot{g}(t)\dot{\mathbf{r}}_1. \quad (10b)$$

The initial conditions are must match these values when $t = 0$,

$$f(0) = 1, \quad \dot{f}(0) = 0 \quad (11a)$$

$$g(0) = 0, \quad \dot{g}(0) = 1. \quad (11b)$$

These form a set of vector differential equations which can be solved for the coefficients f and g . Although they are time dependent, we will drop the function arguments henceforth. However, it is important to remember that these ‘‘coefficients’’ are actually functions of \mathbf{r}_1 and $\dot{\mathbf{r}}_1$, because we will need to take the partial derivatives for the Jacobian.

There are different forms for the Lagrange coefficients; we use the eccentric anomaly formulation [5],

$$f = 1 - \frac{a}{r_1}(1 - \cos \Delta E) \quad (12a)$$

$$g = t - \sqrt{\frac{a^3}{\mu}}(\Delta E - \sin \Delta E) \quad (12b)$$

$$\dot{f} = \frac{-\sqrt{\mu a} \sin \Delta E}{r_2 r_1} \quad (12c)$$

$$\dot{g} = 1 - \frac{a}{r_2}(1 - \cos \Delta E), \quad (12d)$$

where a is the semimajor axis, $\Delta E = E_2 - E_1$ is the change in eccentric anomaly between the two points, and μ is the gravitational constant. In order to use these coefficients, the semimajor axis and change in eccentric anomaly must be computed from r_1 and r_2 , and the latter requires the application of Kepler's equation among other things. Typically in this application a Newton method is used to solve Kepler's equation at each point. It is important to note that E_2 must be greater than E_1 , and it must include whole orbits, that is to say, each whole orbit adds another 2π to the change. No angle normalization (reduction to a range $-\pi$ to π or 0 to 2π) for E_2 is permitted here.

The Jacobian matrix needed for the transformation of variables in this problem is 3×3

$$J = \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_2}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{r}}_1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial r_{2I}}{\partial v_{1I}} & \frac{\partial r_{2I}}{\partial v_{1J}} & \frac{\partial r_{2I}}{\partial v_{1K}} \\ \frac{\partial r_{2J}}{\partial v_{1I}} & \frac{\partial r_{2J}}{\partial v_{1J}} & \frac{\partial r_{2J}}{\partial v_{1K}} \\ \frac{\partial r_{2K}}{\partial v_{1I}} & \frac{\partial r_{2K}}{\partial v_{1J}} & \frac{\partial r_{2K}}{\partial v_{1K}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (13)$$

where derivatives of each of the three Cartesian components I, J, K are shown. This matrix is one 3×3 block of the 6×6 state transition matrix for orbit dynamics. It was computed by Battin [6], and Battin's presentation was untangled by Arora et al. [7]. Equations (38)–(44), (47), and (50) of the latter publication form a clear algorithm from inputs $r_1, r_2, \Delta t$ and f (eq. (12a)), g (eq. (12b)), \dot{f} (eq. (12c)), \dot{g} (eq. (12d)) and the semimajor axis a ; the latter set come out of the Lambert solver

$$U_1 = -\frac{r_1 r_2 \dot{f}}{\sqrt{\mu}} \quad (14a)$$

$$U_2 = r_1(1 - f) \quad (14b)$$

$$U_3 = \sqrt{\mu}(t - g) \quad (14c)$$

$$U_4 = U_1 U_3 - \frac{1}{2}(U_2^2 - U_3^2/a) \quad (14d)$$

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{\mathbf{r}_1 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_1}{\sqrt{\mu}} \quad (14e)$$

$$\sigma_2 = \frac{\mathbf{r}_2 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_2}{\sqrt{\mu}} \quad (14f)$$

$$\chi = \frac{t\sqrt{\mu}}{a} + \sigma_2 - \sigma_1 \quad (14g)$$

$$U_5 = a \left(\frac{1}{6} \chi^3 - U_3 \right) \quad (14h)$$

$$\bar{C} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu}} (3U_5 - \chi U_4 - \sqrt{\mu} U_2 t) \quad (14i)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_2}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{r}}_1} = \frac{r_1}{\mu} (1 - f) [(\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1) \otimes \dot{\mathbf{r}}_1 - (\dot{\mathbf{r}}_2 - \dot{\mathbf{r}}_1) \otimes \mathbf{r}_1] + \frac{\bar{C}}{\mu} \dot{\mathbf{r}}_2 \otimes \dot{\mathbf{r}}_1 + gI \quad (14j)$$

where I is the 3×3 identity matrix and “ \otimes ” represents the outer product, forming a 3×3 matrix from two 3-vectors.

THE BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEM

All solutions

The inverse image needed for the transformation of variables is a matter of finding the correct initial velocity $\dot{\mathbf{r}}_1$ such that together with the known fragmentation location \mathbf{r}_1 , and the elapsed time t , the correct final location \mathbf{r}_2 is obtained. That is, t , \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 are given, and $\dot{\mathbf{r}}_1$ must be found. This is the classic Lambert problem, or two-point boundary value problem for orbit mechanics. Over the centuries since it was first posed, numerous methods have been developed for solving this problem. Some methods do better on or are only applicable for certain kinds of orbits, for example, short arcs, bound orbits, or those that go less than a whole orbit; for this application, we cannot restrict the kinds of orbits.

Between any two position vectors, an orbit can go in one of two directions. If the transfer angle is less than 180 degrees, the arc is considered *short* way, if between 180 and 360 degrees, it is considered *long* way. Note the terms refer to the angle; the amount of time is the same in both cases, as assumed in the problem. If the earth center and the two points are colinear, there is no unique solution because the plane is undetermined, but the planar elements a , e and true anomaly can be determined.

If the trajectory passes the initial point \mathbf{r}_1 at least once before t has elapsed, the trajectory is a *whole orbit* trajectory (customarily called “multi-revolution”); it will pass \mathbf{r}_1 N times before the elapsed time is up. This corresponds to $N \geq 1$ in eq. (1) in the illustration of the antipodal bands. If it does not pass \mathbf{r}_1 before the elapsed time is up, it is a *zero orbit* case. All possible cases of non-negative integer N need to be examined in the Lambert algorithm.

A zero orbit trajectory can be of any conic section, but a whole orbit must be a bound orbit, i.e., circular or elliptical. While there is a solution for a zero orbit trajectory for any pair of points and time, assuming unlimited speed is possible, the whole orbit case has a minimum time. As N increases, this minimum time increases. Therefore, the search for solution is finite; if N is high enough that there are no solutions because the elapsed time is less than the minimum time, then no higher value of N need be searched.

Our application is unique among typical uses of Lambert solvers: we must obtain all solutions for a given set of boundary conditions and time; that is, all inverse images are necessary to form the sum in eq. (9). This includes all conic sections circular, elliptical, parabolic, and hyperbolic, both directions, and all revolution counts.

The preceding exposition refers to the mathematical solution of the Lambert problem. Not all mathematical solutions are physical solutions; if the geocentric distance becomes less than the radius of the earth over the trajectory, it is not physically possible. Therefore, after determining a solution

mathematically, it must be checked for minimum geocentric distance. If it is a whole orbit trajectory, that is the perigee radius. If it is zero orbit, and the trajectory crosses perigee, then again the perigee radius is the minimum geocentric distance. If the trajectory doesn't cross perigee, then the minimum geocentric distance is given by the smaller of the distances at the endpoints r_1 or r_2 .

Another possible physical limitation is the velocity. If the escape velocity is not a possibility because, for instance, the energy of the fragmentation is known to be too low, then the unbound (parabolic and hyperbolic) orbits need not be considered. A velocity limit means that after a certain amount of time, there is a lower limit on N above zero, because the orbit needs a high enough orbital period to have that low an N . For example, if r_1 and r_2 are antipodal, then after one day, $N = 1$ is only possible if there is enough velocity to reach a 16 hour orbit from the fragmentation location.

Regardless of the Lambert algorithm used, a solver is always necessary, because all algorithms involve some sort of root solving of a function that is not invertible analytically. The solver is typically a standard algorithm such as a Newton method (if a derivative is available), or a bisection solver.

Lambert algorithm

While investigating different Lambert algorithms, we took into account the above considerations, together with the degree of testing that the algorithm had been subject to. We developed both Battin's hypergeometric [6] method and Gooding's method [8]. We settled on Battin's method as it was giving more consistently complete sets of solutions. A core Lambert algorithm should compute a and ΔE ; the Lagrange coefficients are then used to solve for the initial velocity using eq. (10a).

The Lambert theorem states that the elapsed time Δt is a function only of semimajor axis (an unknown in the Lambert problem), the sum of the geocentric distances $r_1 + r_2$, the chord length $c = |r_2 - r_1|$, whether the object went the long way (past the antipodal line) or the short way, and how many times N it passed the initial position r_1 before the elapsed time. The Battin method computes a "normalized time," the time times the mean motion of the minimum energy orbit (see (7.32) in [6])

$$\sqrt{\frac{\mu}{a_m^3}} \Delta t = \frac{2\pi N}{(1-x^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{4}{3} \eta^3 {}_2F_1\left(3, 1; \frac{5}{2}; S_1\right) + 4\lambda\eta, \quad (15)$$

where N is the whole orbit count. Other quantities needed are computed in succession

$$s = \frac{r_1 + r_2 + c}{2} \quad (16)$$

$$a_m = \frac{s}{2} \quad (17)$$

$$\lambda = \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{c}{s}} \quad (18)$$

$$y = \sqrt{1 - \lambda^2(1 - x^2)} \quad (19)$$

$$\eta = y - \lambda x \quad (20)$$

$$S_1 = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \lambda - x\eta); \quad (21)$$

a_m is the minimal semimajor axis. The sign for λ is chosen on the short way/long way information; if the short way, the positive sign is taken, if the long way, the negative. The variable $x > -1$ is the

Figure 2. Typical curve of normalized time versus x by whole orbit N ; short way only shown

unknown that must be solved. The function ${}_2F_1$ is a hypergeometric function and was computed using the Gnu Scientific Library [9]. The gravitation constant is given by μ .

The variable x must be found that satisfies this equation. Many root-solving techniques can make use of the derivative of the right hand side. The derivative of the hypergeometric function is another hypergeometric function*, so the derivative of the right hand side of eq. (15) is

$$\frac{6\pi Nx}{(1-x^2)^{5/2}} - \frac{4}{5}(px + \eta)\eta^3 {}_2F_1\left(4, 2; \frac{7}{2}; S_1\right) + 4\lambda p + 4p\eta^2 {}_2F_1\left(3, 1; \frac{5}{2}; S_1\right) \quad (22)$$

with

$$p = \frac{x\lambda^2}{y} - \lambda. \quad (23)$$

For the zero orbit case, presuming there is enough velocity, there is no minimum time to get to another point (except the time it takes light to travel between the points), so all solutions must be found. On the other hand, for the whole orbit case $N \geq 1$, there is a minimum time $t_{\min}(N)$ such that if $\Delta t < t_{\min}(N)$ is less, no solution exists. For each additional whole orbit, this minimum time increases $t_{\min}(N+1) > t_{\min}(N)$, so if it is found for a particular N that the minimum time is too high, the search with increasing N may be terminated for the input conditions.

Figure 2 shows a curve of normalized time versus x by whole orbit N for

$$\mathbf{r}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 7278.1363 \\ 0.0 \\ 0.0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ km}, \quad \mathbf{r}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -10000.0 \\ 3750.0 \\ 0.0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ km}. \quad (24)$$

*<http://functions.wolfram.com/HypergeometricFunctions/Hypergeometric2F1/20/01/05/>

For this case, each normalized time unit represents 1332.05s, so 24 hours is 64.862 normalized time units, represented by the dashed line in the figure. The plot shows only short way curves; it is clear that $N = 0$ has one such solution and each of $N = 1, \dots, 9$ has two solutions. The minimum time for $N \geq 10$ is too large for there to be any solutions for 24 hours. The plot of long way curves looks similar and doubles the number of solutions. The Battin variable is greater than or equal to one $x \geq 1$ for unbound orbits, which is only possible if $N = 0$.

Solving for orbits

The transformation of variables technique for density calculation requires that *every* Lambert solution be found, the inverse images of the initial value problem, together with the forward Jacobian determinant, be computed. There means for each whole orbit count N , all short and long way solutions. For every set of boundary conditions r_1, r_2 and elapsed time Δt , there is one of each for $N = 0$ and two of each for $N \geq 1$, as can be seen in fig. 2.

The normalized time is a known and easily computed function of x as is its derivative, so we tried a standard univariate Newton solver to find the roots [9]. Because the function is not defined for $x \leq -1$, a Newton solver, which is an unconstrained optimization, is not ideal. It is easy to find cases where a guess of a valid x will produce a derivative such that the next iteration of the Newton method gives an invalid value $x \leq -1$. At other points, the solver seemed to miss the solution entirely. Therefore, we switched to a hybrid bracketing/bisection method. In this approach, the solver moves toward the extreme values of x (depending on the derivative of the function at the current evaluation point), halving the distance to the boundaries $x = \pm 1$ until it has bracketed the desired value. At that point, it switches strategy to a standard bisection method until the solution is found with the desired accuracy. This was found to be highly reliable, with no convergence failures or other missed solutions.

The accuracy of the solution is an interesting topic. Typically a tolerance, either relative or absolute, on the accuracy of any kind of iterative solver must be specified. In the early phases, we checked the accuracy of all solutions by propagating the found orbit from the initial time to the final time, and compare the distance between that propagated point and the desired r_2 . We logged all distances that exceed 1 km. Sometimes, there were errors of thousands of kilometers. By increasing the absolute and relative tolerance from 10^{-4} to 10^{-5} , so that $|x_1 - x_0| < 10^{-5}(1 + x_0)$ terminates the iteration, one error of more than 2000 km was reduced to 20 cm, but the resultant velocity \dot{r}_1 did not change by much. As orbit elapsed times become longer, the errors increase and the tolerance must decrease. For the sake of computation time, the accuracy checker was eliminated for production runs.

Once the solver has found a value of x that solves eq. (15), the semimajor axis a and change in eccentric anomaly ΔE may be found. The semimajor axis is computed from a_m using x ,

$$a = \frac{a_m}{1 - x^2} \quad (25)$$

and the change in eccentric anomaly during the elapsed time period

$$\Delta E = 2\pi N + 2(\arccos x \pm \arccos y), \quad (26)$$

where the sign on the final term is determined by the short (-)/long (+) way information. If $x > 1$, the orbit is hyperbolic and the cosines become hyperbolic cosines. The inclusion of the whole orbit count N is important here, as correct (non-normalized) angle is necessary to compute the rest of

Figure 3. Color scale used for density maps

the orbit. From the determined a and ΔE , the Lagrange coefficients eq. (10) may be rearranged to solve for \dot{r}_1 ,

$$\dot{r}_1 = \frac{r_2 - f r_1}{g}. \quad (27)$$

It is this velocity \dot{r}_1 that is needed for the look-up in the velocity distribution function at the fragmentation for the density transformation. Also needed is the Jacobian determinant of the forward map; by calculating \dot{f} and \dot{g} , the complete set of inputs to the Jacobian calculation eq. (14) is available.

Even when $\Delta t > t_{\min}$ for a given N , there may be no physical solution, for any of the four mathematical solutions possible. However, as N increases and t_{\min} increases, there may be mathematical and physical solutions possible. In the case plotted in fig. 2, there are 38 mathematical solutions and two physical solutions (one each short and long way) for each of $N = 0, 7, 8$, and 9 , and no more, for a total of eight. The corresponding curves are marked in red on the plot; only one each of the whole orbit solutions is a physical solution, so there are four total short way solutions. There are also four long way solutions, ungraphed.

Collinear points $r_1 \parallel r_2$ represent a particular problem for Lambert solvers. Most significantly, an orbital plane is not determined by collinear points, so only the planar elements a, e may be solved. This means that the inverse image of the initial value problem is a continuum of points, so the sum in eq. (9) must be replaced by an integral. Since we did not do this calculation, this shows up as a gap (black line) in the density plot.

SIMULATION AND RESULTS

In order to learn better the nature and structure of the fragment distribution, to confirm the bands, and to find other concentrated density areas beyond the pinch points, we studied the case of a satellite in a 900 km altitude circular orbit that fragments. From the computation of all physically possible Lambert solutions, the inverse images of each r_2 , together with the corresponding forward Jacobian determinant, a density is obtained for each point, converted to a color, and rendered in a plot.

The maximum delta- v from the fragmentation the circular speed of the object is 2 km/s. This makes a maximum possible inertial speed of 9.4 km/s which is less than the escape velocity, so parabolic and hyperbolic orbits are not possible in this particular simulation. There is constant density distribution for all velocities within the limit; this is sometimes called a “top hat” distribution.

While the method works for points anywhere in space, for presentation purposes and to keep the computation time down, only points in the original orbital plane of the simulated satellite were computed. The figures extend from -20000 km from the center of the earth on the left, antipodal to

Figure 4. Density in the original orbital plane half to three hours (by half hour) after fragmentation

Figure 5. Density in the original orbital plane 3.5 to 6 hours (by half hour) after fragmentation

Figure 6. Density in the original orbital plane 7 to 12 hours (by one hour) after fragmentation

Figure 7. Density in the original orbital plane 14 to 24 hours (by one hour) after fragmentation

Figure 8. Density in the original orbital plane 26 to 36 hours (by one hour) after fragmentation

the fragmentation location, to +10000 km on the right where the fragmentation is. In the perpendicular direction, it extends ± 15000 km. The asymmetric plot in the horizontal direction was chosen deliberately because most of the interesting density variations are antipodal to the fragmentation location. The mesh points evaluated are every 30 km in both directions.

There were a total of a little over one million points evaluated for each picture. For a post-fragmentation elapsed time of 24 hours, the number of Lambert solutions at each point varied from zero (about 14% of the points) up to 31 (about 0.9% of the points). There are an average of 11.33 Lambert solutions per point at this time. The number of solutions obtained is a significant indicator of the density, and the sharp density changes observed are largely due to the appearance and disappearance of solutions.

The densities obtained are either zero, where there is no solution, or in the range of 10^{-14}km^{-3} to 10^{-9}km^{-3} or so. A scale is shown in fig. 3; the zero density points are plotted as black. The lowest positive densities are plotted in blue, brightening from black to the brightest blue. The colors are calibrated on two scales, per cubic kilometer, and per earth volume; the latter gives numbers nearer one. From $7.5 \times 10^{-13}\text{km}^{-3}$ through $1.0 \times 10^{-10}\text{km}^{-3}$, the hue changes on a logarithmic scale from blue to magenta to yellow. Densities above $5.0 \times 10^{-10}\text{km}^{-3}$ are shown as white. The densities are normalized number densities, meaning that the number of fragments expected in a volume is the integral of the density that volume, multiplied by the total number of fragments.

Figures 4 to 8 show the computed density map every half hour for the first six hours, then every hour to twelve hours, and finally every two hours to thirty six. There are many structures apparent from these figures. Of course, the bands are noticeable. During the very earliest times, Jehn's phase A, which lasts approximately one original orbital period, the cloud forms into a banana shape (including the stem!) that has long been recognized [10]. Then, in phase B, the leading front of the cloud curves around to make a full circle back to the pinch point at about three hours, or two orbital periods. This is the first band.

Meanwhile, the outer tail of the lowest density region is moving outward. As time goes on, the leading front keeps cycling, making new bands at the same radius (approximately the radius of the original radius), with the old bands moving outward. After several hours, it is very difficult to see the leading front because it is so narrow.

The "anti-pinch line," or "anti-pinch wedge" as it has been called, is distinctly noticeable after about an hour. It is caused by the appearance of two $N = 0$ (zero orbit) solutions; because the earth blocks long-way solutions that are too close to the original point, the double solution is only possible near the antipodal line. As the first (outer) band moves out of the field of view at about three hours, it takes with it most of that concentrated density. As the new bands form, they each have the concentrated line, but that region of concentration does not persist between bands; it is more a series of line segments.

As new bands are created and move outward, they overlap the old bands, and the boundaries of the bands are clearly visible in this case as superposition of the individual densities. Between the bands, the zero-density gaps on the antipodal side start out very broad, and gradually fill in. At around 18 hours, the bands in the middle are just starting to completely overlap. Notice that the triangular shape gaps are more on the upper half plane than the lower.

Although it is difficult to see at this resolution, the "fronts" of the bands have a sudden drop off in density with increasing radial distance, from the very highest density to actually or almost nothing, while the climb back up in density is much more gradual. Look for the thin magenta line along the outer edge of the band at hours eight through twenty.

It bears reminding that this is a two-body simulation only; perturbations will certainly alter the appearance, and likely have the effect of smearing together sharp density contrasts, most notably, the bands.

At 24 hours, the positive densities vary from $1.23 \times 10^{-14} \text{km}^{-3}$ to $1.14 \times 10^{-8} \text{km}^{-3}$, a factor of almost one million. This significantly exceeds Hujsak's observation of four orders of magnitude variation; contrary to his belief, it can be explained without perturbations, since this simulation was two-body only.

APPLICATION

This study is a pathfinder in showing how to analyze the structure of a debris cloud, and how it evolves in time. Although orbit propagation, as *point dynamics*, has a rich history that stretches back several hundred years, very few have thought about *cloud dynamics*. Although the governing dynamics is the same, the view is very different; knowing that the unperturbed initial value problem for point dynamics gives a conic section does not prepare one for the results shown in the figures. These results just scratch the surface of the phenomena resulting.

There is nothing in these results that require the distribution be of actual pieces from a fragmentation. They could as well be a probability distribution, originating from, say uncertain propulsion. In that case, the isotropic distribution assumed for the figures is probably not applicable, but as noted previously, it is a relatively simple to swap out initial velocity distributions and recompute density, one the Lambert velocity solutions and Jacobian determinants have been computed and saved. Most of those who have studied density propagation have been interested in the uncertain propulsion (or sensing) problem; they usually assume a highly peaked and possible even normal distribution. Unfortunately, orbit dynamics in Cartesian coordinates rapidly makes a hash of that assumption!

There are many potential improvements and extensions possible. First, the third dimension would be very interesting, and that requires significantly more computation. This merits an investigation of computational speed improvements; something like the differential Lambert [7] solution might be very helpful. However, a caution on differential Lambert is necessary. As we have seen, quantitative change in the number of solutions at some edges, when a solution appears or disappears, and a differential method might miss this. Another approach would be to use an adaptive mesh, so that vast regions without solutions can be skipped, instead of evaluating on a lattice grid. Although, in regions where there are few or no solutions, the computation goes much faster as it is.

The effect of perturbations, notably J_2 and drag, would make an interesting alteration to the picture. We anticipate that the inclusion of perturbations will smear some of the sharp changes in density and associated structures seen in the figures. In the same way that the earth acts as an occlusion of the orbits, cutting the set of solutions from the mathematical to the physical, the presence of atmospheric drag will effectively expand the radius of the earth from that point of view by removing the lowest orbits, especially for longer elapsed time periods.

CONCLUSION

Cloud dynamics of orbits is different for the traditional point orbital dynamics, yet uses its results. A transformation of variables approach can show structure and evolution of a fragmentation previously unnoticed. The well-known pinch point is observed, and a concentration of density on the antipodal line, also noted by other researchers, is plainly visible. Antipodal bands, which can

be motivated by elementary orbit mechanics, are the most obvious structure noticeable, and are even obvious with a simple Monte Carlo simulation, yet seem to be unnoted previously. These bands correspond to the number of revolutions the fragment makes over the elapsed time interval. They increase in number, thin out, and increase in radius as the time elapsed increases. Much finer structure is visible; even more remains to investigate in detail.

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